

Automated symbolic geodesics classification in spherically symmetric black holes using first order cellular automata

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Abstract

Some recent works in theoretical high-energy physics have focused on classification of circular geodesics of charged particles in the background of spherically symmetric charged black holes. These studies reveal a lot about the black holes such as phase transitions. But obtaining this classification by means of symbolic computation is a highly tedious and time-consuming process. This is so because, in the actual implementation, obtaining the solution requires the calculation of reduced Gröbner bases for large polynomial systems which is proven to be of doubly exponential time complexity using the standard Buchberger algorithm. In this article, I present an algorithm that takes the metric of the black hole as an input and automatically derives the classification with the help of Gröbner bases using first-order cellular automata. Detailed analyses of the asymptotic complexity have also been discussed, which show the feasibility of the proposed algorithm.

1 Introduction and related work

A black hole is a region of spacetime that is so strong in terms of its gravitational pull that nothing, not even light, can escape from it [3]. Einstein was the first one to conclude, from his field equations, that the mass and the field existent in a certain spacetime can cause its geometry to yield a curve, or in other words, deform [5]. Then Schwarzschild came up with a vacuum solution to the Einstein field equations [3] that exhibited singularities in spacetime [6], known as the event horizon, causing it to be a black hole. Now one knows even more practically relevant vacuum solutions such as black holes with charge [7], rotating black holes [8], black holes with length scale features [9], black holes with

additional non-curvy 'dents' (known as Gauss-Bonnet gravity) [10] etc. Each of these solutions have certain characteristics in terms of some special trajectories around the black holes, known as geodesics. Geodesics are those paths that can be travelled by two 'locally parallel' particles around the manifold. These have been studied deeply and characteristically for most of the solutions to the Einstein field equations [11, 12, 13, 14].

Another set of interesting properties which are associated with the black holes are the thermodynamic properties [15]. An important and interesting thermodynamic property of the black holes is the heat capacity. The reason of such a high interest is that heat capacity varies from one type of black hole to another. While the heat capacity of the Schwarzschild black hole in flat space time is known to be always negative, that of the Reissner-Nördstrom black hole in anti de Sitter spacetime is positive in some regions of the parameter space and negative in others. Davies showed that phase transitions occur in black holes and a second order phase transition (SOPT) takes place when the black hole parameters follow the relation [17]

$$\left(\frac{Q}{M}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{9}{4}\right)^2 \Lambda M^2 + \frac{3}{4}$$

where Q is the charge of the black hole, M is the mass of the black hole, and Λ is the cosmological constant. In general, the thermodynamic phase structure of the black hole includes a line of first order phase transitions ending in a second order phase transitions. Surprisingly, there are visible criticalities matching between the existence of circular orbits around a black hole and the second order phase transition points for the Reissner-Nördstrom anti de Sitter metric [18]. It is still unknown whether or not it can be generalised for other types of black holes. For this, one may need to explore similar analyses for different other kinds of black holes. Precisely, one needs to find all possible types of circular geodesics for a given black hole metric.

But this is a computationally bulky and time-consuming task for certain types of black holes. This is because, as will be shown in section 2.2, one needs to solve a fairly large system of polynomial inequalities. In a computer algebra system like Mathematica, such problems are solved using cylindrical algebraic decomposition and Gröbner basis based algorithms [19]. For Gröbner basis computation, an efficient version of the Buchberger's algorithm is used. In literature, there are several other algorithms asymptotically faster than this; namely the F_4 and the F_5 algorithms [20, 21], the latter being the fastest known till date.

In one equivalent version of the F_5 algorithm, Gaussian elimination has been used [22]. It has been shown that the Gaussian elimination can be solved by reducing it to an equivalent instance of the matrix multiplication problem [23]. In this context, there have been several algorithms which have been suggested for this [24, 25, 26, 27, 28], progressively improving upon the asymptotic time complexity. The lowest possible bound on the time complexity, i.e. $O(n^2)$, n

being the size of matrix, can be achieved for some well-known and frequently dealt-with cases [29] with the assumption of additive complexity measure [39].

A computational alternative to further reduce the asymptotic complexity is the use of data-parallel discrete structures such as cellular automata. Owing to their information scrambling properties, cellular automata find a wide range of applications such as cryptography [31, 32], convolutional neural networks [30], emulation of Turing-complete machines [1, 2] etc. A new direction of applications of cellular automata could be to model highly scaling data-parallel computational systems and design faster algorithms based on the same.

In this article, a cellular automata based symbolic algorithm has been presented that takes the characterising lapse function (defined in section 2.2) of the black hole as input and gives a logical expression as an output that helps one see the classification of circular orbits in the same. The rest of this article is organised as follows. In section 2, discrete structures such as first-order cellular automata, groups, rings, fields, ideals, polynomial rings etc. have been discussed and explained in some introductory detail. Also, a brief introduction to black holes and circular orbits of charged particles around them, has been presented for one to fully understand the statement of the problem. In section 3, the proposed algorithm has been framed step-by-step in a bottom-up approach. In section 4, performance of the algorithm in terms of time complexity has been discussed in some details. The article has been concluded in section 5.

2 Background

In this section, mathematical structures such as first-order cellular automata, groups, rings, fields, ideals, polynomial rings and reductions etc. have been discussed. Also, a brief background on spherically-symmetric black holes and circular orbits of charged particles around them has been presented. The main objective is to provide enough foundations based on which the problem statement has been framed and the solution has also been suggested.

2.1 Formal definition of first-order cellular automata

Any n -dimensional r -neighbourhood first-order **cellular automata (CA)** can be defined as a 4-tuple (S, Q_t, N, f) where $S \subseteq \mathbb{K}$, known as the set of states (\mathbb{K} is a field, an algebraic structure defined in section 2.3); Q_t is an $l_1 \times l_2 \times l_3 \cdots \times l_n$ matrix for an instance of time t , where $\forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \forall i_k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, l_k\}$,

$Q_t[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n] \in S$; N is an $r \times n$ matrix known as the neighbourhood matrix; and finally $f : S^{r+1} \rightarrow S$, known as the transition function. Here the future state of a cellular automaton is defined in the following way

$$\forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \forall i_k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, l_k\},$$

$$Q_{t+1}[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n] = f(Q_t[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n], h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_r)$$

where $h_m = Q_t[\{(i_k + N[m, k]) \bmod l_k\} \forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, l_m\}]$
 $\forall m \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, r\}$.

A special case where $n = 1, r = 2, S = \{0, 1\}, N = (1, -1)^T$, the cellular automaton becomes an elementary cellular automaton. The decimal equivalent of the binary number formed by an ordered sequence of the images of the function f of an elementary cellular automaton is said to be its 'rule', or the 'Wolfram rule'. An example running of rule 110 cellular automaton is graphically illustrated in figure 1 [2]. Also, I hereby would refer to the sequence $Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4 \dots$ as the temporal evolution of a cellular automaton, the matrix Q_1 as the seed of the machine. Another classical example of a two dimensional cellular automaton is shown in figure 2, known as the 'Conway's Game of Life' [1], whose transition function is verbally described as follows.

1. Any live cell with fewer than two live neighbours dies, as if by underpopulation.
2. Any live cell with two or three live neighbours lives on to the next generation.
3. Any live cell with more than three live neighbours dies, as if by overpopulation.
4. Any dead cell with exactly three live neighbours becomes a live cell, as if by reproduction.

In section 3, algorithms for solving matrix multiplication problem and the problem of finding the Gröbner basis with some parallelisation using cellular automata have been discussed. There is where this formal definition of CA has been meticulously followed. But at the same time, it is important to know in what context these algorithms will be used in. For that, a brief introduction to circular geodesics in the background of spherically symmetric black holes is there in section 2.2.

2.2 Classification of circular orbits around black holes

In general relativity, the spacetime is believed to be a continuous and differential manifold, defined by a distance function, the metric tensor, or simply *the metric*. This metric, often mathematically denoted as a two-dimensional matrix $g_{\mu\nu}$, where μ and ν denote the indices of the spacetime variables, simply shows how to calculate the distance between any points on the manifold. For example, the usual Euclidean distance metric leads us to a subset of the Minkowski flat spacetime, where only classical and special relativistic phenomena are defined. Essential mathematical machinery in the form of curvature-defining parameters

Figure 1: A demonstration of the rule 110 cellular automaton [2]. The first row shows the transition rules. It is noteworthy of the binary number formed of the outputs, whose decimal equivalent is rule 110. The subsequent grid shows the temporal evolution, where the initial seed consists of a single one and rest all zeroes.

Figure 2: A demonstration of the Game Of Life cellular automaton [1]. The first grid shows the seed, and the subsequent grids show the temporal evolution of the same. This is known as a 'glider'.

such as the Christoffel's symbols $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}$, Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, Ricci scalar R , the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ define the degree of curvature encountered in the parallel transport of the particles travelling along the corresponding manifold. Detailed mathematical background pertaining to these is given in [4]. The *Einstein's field equations*, a set of equations fundamental to the theory of general relativity, dictate the effect of "mass", i.e. the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$, on the curvature of the spacetime manifold. The field equations in geometrized units (Newton's gravitational constant $G = 1$ and speed of light $c = 1$) are as follows

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

where Λ is the cosmological constant. If the case be that the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu} = 0$, the equations become the *vacuum field equations* and the solutions to these are known as *Einstein's manifolds*. One such family of classic examples of Einstein's manifolds is the following generic metric of the spherically-symmetric 4-dimensional black hole.

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 f(r) + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \quad (2)$$

where $f(r)$ is known to be lapse function of the black hole. Table 1 shows the various types of black holes with the respective lapse functions. But these are not the only ones available. There are others such as with the addition of the Gauss-Bonnet term [33], BTZ black holes [34] etc. In these the lapse functions take even more complicated form, and consequently show various other types of sophisticated features. Among the ones shown in table 1, only Reissner-Nördstrom, Reissner-Nördstrom anti de-Sitter, Bardeen, and Ayon-Beato-Garcia black holes [11] have charges in them. So only for these cases, the external charges projected towards them are expected to interact.

Table 1: Various types of black holes along with the lapse functions. Here M is the mass of the black hole, Q is the charge of the black hole, $l = -\frac{3}{\Lambda^2}$, Λ being the cosmological constant and g is a charge parameter associated with Bardeen black holes.

Black hole	Lapse function $f(r)$
Schwarzschild	$1 - \frac{2M}{r}$
Reissner-Nördstrom	$1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{Q^2}{r^2}$
Schwarzschild anti de-Sitter	$1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{r^2}{l^2}$
Reissner-Nördstrom anti de-Sitter	$1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{Q^2}{r^2} + \frac{r^2}{l^2}$
Bardeen	$1 - \frac{2Mr^2}{(g^2+r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$
Bardeen anti de-Sitter	$1 - \frac{2Mr^2}{(g^2+r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{r^2}{l^2}$
Ayon-Beato-Garcia	$1 - \frac{2Mr^2}{(g^2+r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{g^2 r^2}{(g^2+r^2)^2}$
Ayon-Beato-Garcia anti de-Sitter	$1 - \frac{2Mr^2}{(g^2+r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{g^2 r^2}{(g^2+r^2)^2} + \frac{r^2}{l^2}$

The Lagrangian of any particle in the background of this black hole is of the form, having chosen $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$,

$$\mathcal{L} = -f(r)\dot{t}^2 + \frac{\dot{r}^2}{f(r)} + r^2\dot{\phi}^2$$

The conserved quantities in such cases are time and angular momentum, as is followed from Euler-Lagrange equations.

$$\dot{t} = -\frac{E}{f(r)}, \dot{\phi} = \frac{L}{r^2}$$

From the above, the Lagrangian is given as,

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{\dot{r}^2 - E^2}{f(r)} + \frac{L^2}{r^2}$$

For charged space-like particles, $\mathcal{L} = -1$, so,

$$\dot{r} = \sqrt{E^2 - \left(1 + \frac{L^2}{r^2}\right)f(r)}$$

Also, for radially dependent metrics, there exists a gauge potential $A_t(r)$ responsible for the electromagnetic interactions. The effective potential $V_{eff}(r)$ of a particle with charge ϵ is then given as

$$V_{eff}(r) = \epsilon A_t(r) + \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{L^2}{r^2}\right)f(r)}$$

The condition for the particle to attain circular orbits around the black holes is

$$\frac{\partial V_{eff}(r)}{\partial r} = 0 \tag{3}$$

which implies that the angular momentum L_{\pm} is given as

$$L_{\pm} = r \sqrt{f(r)f'(r) \left(\frac{\epsilon A_t'(r) \pm \sqrt{4f(r)f'(r) + \epsilon^2 A_t'(r)^2 - 2}}{2f(r)f'(r) - 1} \right)^2 - 1} \tag{4}$$

Now there are constraints on radius of the circular orbits r and other parameters associated with the lapse function $f(r)$ and potential function $A_t(r)$ arising from the condition that L_{\pm} should be real. To explain further, the following functions are introduced,

$$a(r) = f(r)f'(r)\epsilon^2 A_t'(r)^2 \left(1 + f'(r)\right) + 2f(r)f'(r) - 1$$

$$b(r) = 2\epsilon f(r)f'(r)$$

$$c(r) = 4f(r)f'(r) + \epsilon^2 A'_t(r)^2 f'(r) - 2$$

So the constraint for the L_{\pm} logically reduces to the following condition.

$$c(r) \geq 0 \wedge \left(a(r) \geq 0 \vee a(r)^2 \leq b(r)^2 c(r) \right) \quad (5)$$

It is notable that some of the lapse functions presented in table 1, such as Schwarzschild and Reissner-Nördstrom black holes, can be represented as rational functions and polynomials in terms of radial coordinate r . For such cases, the system represented by equation 5 is a polynomial system of inequalities. But for those such as Bardeen black holes, the system needs to be further resolved by solving for the internal surds that are present in the lapse function, which will potentially increase the number of polynomial inequalities. The number of inequalities scale for lapse functions containing the Gauss-Bonnet term [33]. Such systems can be solved by Mathematica, a famous computer algebra software, which uses an optimisation of the Buchberger's algorithm [36] to solve for the Gröbner bases of the polynomials involved in the system. But Buchberger's algorithm is doubly exponential in terms of time complexity [35] which makes the system extremely slow and inefficient. The fastest known algorithm for the computation of the Gröbner basis is the F_5 algorithm [21] whose matrix based version is discussed in section 2.3 with apt mathematical background.

2.3 F_5 algorithm to compute Gröbner basis

Before the description of the F_5 algorithm, it is necessary to describe and revisit some basic formalisms of the group theory. A **group** (G, \cdot) is a set G together with a binary operation \cdot , where the following properties hold good.

1. *Closure*: $\forall a, b \in G, a \cdot b \in G$
2. *Associativity*: $\forall a, b, c \in G, a \cdot (b \cdot c) = (a \cdot b) \cdot c$
3. *Existence of identity element*: $\exists e \in G, \forall a \in G, a \cdot e = e \cdot a = a$
4. *Existence of inverse*: $\forall a \in G, \exists b \in G, a \cdot b = b \cdot a = e$

A group (G, \cdot) is said to be an **Abelian group** if it satisfies *commutativity* i.e., $\forall a, b \in G, a \cdot b = b \cdot a$. A **ring** $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a set R equipped with two binary operations $+, \cdot$ that satisfies the following properties.

1. $(R, +)$ is an abelian group.
2. $\exists e_M \in R, \forall a \in R, e_M \cdot a = a \cdot e_M = a$
3. R is associative with respect to \cdot i.e., $\forall a, b, c \in R, a \cdot (b \cdot c) = (a \cdot b) \cdot c$
4. The operation \cdot is distributive over $+$ i.e., $\forall a, b, c \in R, \left(a \cdot (b + c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c \right) \wedge \left((b + c) \cdot a = b \cdot a + c \cdot a \right)$

For such a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, a subset $I \subseteq R$ is said to be an **ideal** if

1. $(I, +)$ is a subgroup of $(R, +)$, i.e. $(I, +)$ is a group and $I \subseteq R$.
2. $\forall r \in R, \forall x \in I, r \cdot x \in I$.

A ring $(F, +, \cdot)$ is said to be a **field** if

1. The operation \cdot is commutative over F i.e., $\forall a, b \in F, a \cdot b = b \cdot a$.
2. $\forall a \in F, \exists b \in F, a \cdot b = b \cdot a = e_M$, where e_M is known as the *multiplicative identity*.

A **monomial** M in n variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is a product $x_1^{\alpha_1} x_2^{\alpha_2} \dots x_n^{\alpha_n}$ where α_i s are non-negative integers. For a monomial $x_1^{\alpha_1} x_2^{\alpha_2} \dots x_n^{\alpha_n}$, the sum $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \dots + \alpha_n$ is known as its **degree**. A **polynomial** in a field K is a sum $c_1 M_1 + c_2 M_2 + \dots + c_p M_p$ where c_i s are non-zero elements of K and M_i s are monomials. The **degree of a polynomial** is the highest degree of its monomials. The set \mathcal{P} of all polynomials in the field K along with polynomial addition and polynomial multiplication operations form a ring known as the **polynomial ring**, denoted as $K[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] = (\mathcal{P}, +, \cdot)$. A **Gröbner basis** of an ideal I in a polynomial ring R is a generating set of I characterised by any of the following properties.

1. The ideal generated by leading terms of polynomials in I equals the ideal generated by the leading terms of polynomials in G .
2. The leading term of any polynomial in I is divisible by the leading term of some polynomial in G .
3. The multivariate division of any polynomial in the polynomial ring R by G gives unique remainder.
4. The multivariate division by G of any polynomial in the ideal I gives the remainder 0.

Let $R = Q[x, y]$ be the ring of bivariate polynomials with rational coefficients and consider the ideals $I = \langle f, g \rangle$ generated by the polynomials,

$$f(x, y) = x^2 - y$$

$$g(x, y) = x^3 - x$$

For this ideal I , one such Gröbner basis is the set $\{x^2 - y, xy - x, y^2 - y\}$. Any set of polynomials may be viewed as a system of polynomial equations by equating the polynomials to zero. The set of the solutions of such a system depends only on the generated ideal, and therefore does not change when the given generating set is replaced by its Gröbner basis, for any ordering, of the generated ideal. Such a solution is known as the *zero of the ideal*.

Given the Gröbner basis G of an ideal I , it has only a finite number of zeros, if and only if, for each variable x , G contains a polynomial with leading monomial that is a power of x (without any other variable appearing in the leading term). If it is the case the number of zeros, counted with multiplicity, is equal to the number of monomials that are not multiples of any leading monomial of G . This number is called the *degree of the ideal*. To know the details of how to compute Gröbner basis, one also needs to revisit the notion of reducibility in polynomials.

Given two polynomials f and g , one says that f is reducible by g if some monomial m in f is a multiple of the leading monomial $lm(g)$ of g . If c is the coefficient of m in f and $m = q \times lm(g)$, then one-step reduction of f by g that associates to f , the polynomial

$$red_1(f, g) = f - \frac{c}{lc(g)} \cdot q \cdot g$$

where $lc(g)$ is the leading coefficient of the polynomial g . If m happens to be the leading monomial of f then one says that f is *lead-reducible* by g . If $red_1(f, g)$ does not exist, then f is said to be *irreducible* by g . Given a finite set G of polynomials and another polynomial f , not necessarily an element of G , one says that f is *reducible* or *lead-reducible* by G if it is reducible or lead-reducible, respectively, by an element g of G . If this is the case, then one defines $red_1(f, G) = red_1(f, g)$. The complete reduction of f by G consists in applying the red_1 function iteratively, until getting a polynomial $red(f, G)$ which is *irreducible* by G . It is called the *normal form* of f by G .

The first ever known algorithm for computing the Gröbner basis G for a given set of polynomials that generates an ideal I , is Buchberger's algorithm [36]. This algorithm is used for solving for Gröbner bases and polynomial systems in the complex field in Mathematica 11.2 [19]. A pseudocode of the algorithm has been shown in algorithm 1. Buchberger's algorithm considers every pair of polynomials (including the ones newly added) individually in each of its iterations, causing it to be EXPSPACE-complete. Precisely, Dubé [35] showed

that for polynomials of n variables and maximum degree d , the number of operations in Buchberger's algorithm is $O(d^{2^n})$. Two of the optimisations that were aimed at the choice of the right selection of pairs (known as the *critical pairs*) and avoiding the other useless reductions resulted in Faugère's F_4 algorithm [20] and F_5 algorithm [21]. These two algorithms perform asymptotically better than the Buchberger's algorithm. In this paper, F_5 algorithm will be considered as a case as it is known to be the fastest one [22]. The pseudocode of the F_5 algorithm is given in algorithm 2. For an ideal generated by m polynomials of n variables with maximum degree D , the number of operations required by F_5 algorithm is $O\left(mD\binom{n+D-1}{D}^\omega\right)$ (ω is the matrix multiplication exponent) which is asymptotically singly exponential in n [22]. The exponent ω also influences the asymptotic complexity as the reduction of the Macaulay matrix to the row echelon form can be solved by an equivalent instance of the matrix multiplication [23]. It was known for long that $\omega < 2.372869$ [27], but it has been proven that ω can be brought down to 2 for fields like integers, reals and complex numbers [29] by using a number-theoretic optimisation encouraged by the additive complexity measure [39]. In the section 2.4, it has been proven that a similar optimisation holds good for polynomial rings as well.

Algorithm 2.1: BUCHBERGERALGORITHM(F)

comment: The input F is a set of polynomials that generates the ideal I

comment: The output G is a Gröbner basis for ideal I

$G \leftarrow F$

while $True$

do $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Choose two polynomials } f_i, f_j \\ g_i := \text{leading term of } f_i \\ g_j := \text{leading term of } f_j \\ S_{ij} := \text{red}\left(a_{ij}\left(\frac{f_i}{g_i} - \frac{f_j}{g_j}\right), G\right) \\ \text{If } S_{ij} \neq 0, G := G \cup \{S_{ij}\} \\ \text{If all possible pairs } (f_i, f_j) \in G \text{ have been considered, then exit from the loop} \end{array} \right.$

return (G)

Algorithm 2.2: F_5 ALGORITHM(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m)

comment: Homogeneous polynomials (f_1, \dots, f_m) with degrees $d_1 \leq \dots \leq d_m$;

comment: a maximal degree D

comment: The output is the elements of degree at most D of the reduced Gröbner bases of

comment: (f_1, \dots, f_i) , for $i = 1, \dots, m$

for $i \leftarrow 1$ **to** n

do $G[i] \leftarrow \phi$

for $d \leftarrow d_1$ **to** D

do $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} M_{d,0} \leftarrow \phi \\ \tilde{M}_{d,0} \leftarrow \phi \\ \text{for } i \leftarrow 1 \text{ to } m \\ \quad \text{if } d < d_i \\ \quad \text{then } M_{d,i} \leftarrow \tilde{M}_{d,i} \\ \quad \text{else if } d = d_i \\ \quad \text{then } M_{d,i} \leftarrow \text{add new form } f_i \text{ to } \tilde{M}_{d,i-1} \text{ with index } (i, 1) \\ \quad \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} M_{d,i} \leftarrow \tilde{M}_{d,i-1} \\ \text{Crit} \leftarrow LT(\tilde{M}_{d-d_i,i-1}) \\ \text{comment: } LT(f) \text{ returns the leading term of the polynomial} \\ \text{for } i \in Rows(M_{d-1,i})/Rows(M_{d-1,i-1}) \\ \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (i, u) \leftarrow index(f) \text{ with} \\ u = x_1, \dots, x_j \text{ and } 1 \leq j_1 \leq \dots \leq j_{d-d_i-1} \leq n \\ \text{do } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{for } j \leftarrow j_{d-d_i-1} \text{ to } n \\ \quad \text{do } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{if } ux_j \in Crit \\ \quad \text{then add the new row } x_j f \text{ with index } (i, ux_j) \text{ in } M_{d,i} \end{array} \right. \\ \text{Compute } \tilde{M}_{d,i} \text{ by Gaussian elimination from } M_{d,i} \\ \text{Add to } G_i \text{ all rows of } \tilde{M}_{d,i} \text{ not reducible by } LT(G_i) \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right.$

Constraints like the one mentioned in equation 5 can be further reduced to a system of polynomial inequalities. The main objective of our scheme shall be to solve this system effectively using the Gröbner basis. As visible in algorithm 2.2, the result is obtained using Gaussian elimination, which reorders the same inequality by means of some lexicographical ordering. Having given the inequalities in the original polynomial system, one can conclude the equivalent inequalities in the Gröbner basis by means of *elementary interval arithmetic*, whose basic unit is the interval. But before defining the same, one must be mathematically wary of the fact that intervals are only defined for a total order. Formally, a *total order* is a relation \leq on a set S such that it satisfies the following properties.

1. **Property of antisymmetry:** $\forall a, b \in S, (a \leq b \wedge b \leq a) \implies a = b.$
2. **Property of transitivity:** $\forall a, b \in S, (a \leq b \wedge b \leq c) \implies a \leq c.$

3. Property of connexity: $\forall a, b \in S, (a \leq b) \vee (b \leq a)$.

For a total order \leq on a set S , an interval $[a, b]$ is the set $K = \{x | a \leq x \leq b\}$. Now operations such as addition, subtraction and multiplication are defined on intervals in the following way [37].

$$[x_1, x_2] + [y_1, y_2] = [x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2]$$

$$[x_1, x_2] - [y_1, y_2] = [x_1 - y_2, x_2 - y_1]$$

$$[x_1, x_2] \cdot [y_1, y_2] = [\min(x_1y_1, x_2y_1, x_1y_2, x_2y_2), \max(x_1y_1, x_2y_1, x_1y_2, x_2y_2)]$$

Since any polynomial only deals with these three operations, only these are required to fulfil the required objective. One can start with the only univariate polynomial in the Gröbner basis, symbolically solve for its roots, and back-substitute these intervals to obtain the resultant classification. An example of the same will be presented in the working example of the proposed algorithm.

2.4 On the optimisation of matrix multiplication exponent

To explain the matrix multiplication algorithm with quadratic time complexity, two of the operations related to the long polynomial division are explained. The long polynomial division algorithm takes into consideration two polynomials $A(x)$ and $B(x) \neq 0$, and returns two polynomials $Q(x)$ and $R(x)$ such that

$$A(x) = B(x)Q(x) + R(x)$$

where $\text{degree}(R(x)) < \text{degree}(B(x))$. The polynomial $Q(x)$ is known as the **quotient**, denoted as $\text{quo}(A, B)$, and the polynomial $R(x)$ is known as the **remainder**, denoted as $\text{rem}(A, B)$. The following lemma reiterates an algebraic identity in bilinear form, which according to the Schonhage's theorem [26], leads to the fact that matrix multiplication is of quadratic time complexity. Performing the quotient and remainder operations may require hash tables and constant time boolean combinational logic, assuming the maximum allowable degree is fixed a priori, resulting in quadratic time complexity following the additive complexity measure [39].

Lemma 2.1. *Given a field \mathbb{K} and two matrices $A, B \in \mathbb{K}^{n \times n}$,*

$$(AB)_{i,j} = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k]B[k][j] = \text{rem} \left(\text{quo} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] \lambda^{(n-1-k)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} B[k][j] \lambda^k, \lambda^{n-1} \right), \lambda \right)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] \lambda^{(n-1-k)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} B[k][j] \lambda^k = \\
& \sum_{k_1=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k_2=0}^{n-1} A[i][k_1] \cdot B[k_2][j] \lambda^{(n-1-k_1+k_2)} = \\
& \lambda^{2(n-1)} \cdot A[i][0] \cdot B[n-1][j] + \lambda^{(2n-3)} \sum_{k=0}^1 A[i][k] B[k+n-2][j] + \\
& \dots + \lambda^n \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} A[i][k] B[k+1][j] + \lambda^{(n-1)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] B[k][j] + \\
& \lambda^{(n-2)} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} A[i][k] B[k-1][j] + \dots + A[i][n-1] B[0][j] \\
& \implies \text{quo} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] \lambda^{(n-1-k)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} B[k][j] \lambda^k, \lambda^{(n-1)} \right) = \\
& \lambda^{(n-1)} \cdot A[i][0] \cdot B[n-1][j] + \lambda^{(n-2)} \sum_{k=0}^1 A[i][k] B[k+n-2][j] \\
& + \dots + \lambda \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} A[i][k] B[k+1][j] + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] B[k][j] \\
& \implies \text{rem} \left(\text{quo} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] \lambda^{(n-1-k)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} B[k][j] \lambda^k, \lambda^{(n-1)} \right), \lambda \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A[i][k] B[k][j]
\end{aligned}$$

□

The above lemma proves the correctness of the matrix multiplication algorithm presented in the pseudocode of the algorithm 2.3. The algorithm presented here is a generic version of a suite of algorithms for the same problem solved for basic fields such as integers, reals, complexes etc. [29] This algorithm is of quadratic time complexity, only according to the additive complexity measure [39], but since in real architectures one encounters sequential implementations with some optimisations such as Karatsuba's algorithm [40].

Algorithm 2.3: MATRIXMULTIPLYGENERIC($A[[0,0]...[n-1,n-1]]$, $B[[0,0]...[n-1,n-1]]$)

```

 $C \leftarrow \{0, 0, 0 \dots (n \text{ times}) \dots 0\}$ 
 $D \leftarrow \{0, 0, 0 \dots (n \text{ times}) \dots 0\}$ 
 $E \leftarrow \{\{0, 0, 0 \dots (n \text{ times}) \dots 0\}, \{0, 0, 0 \dots (n \text{ times}) \dots 0\}, \dots (n \text{ times}) \dots \{0, 0, 0 \dots (n \text{ times}) \dots 0\}\}$ 
for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $n - 1$ 
  do  $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{for } j \leftarrow 0 \text{ to } n - 1 \\ \text{do } C[i] \leftarrow C[i] \cdot \lambda + A[i][j] \end{array} \right.$ 
for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $n - 1$ 
  do  $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{for } i \leftarrow 0 \text{ to } n - 1 \\ \text{do } D[j] \leftarrow D[j] \cdot \lambda + B[n - 1 - i][j] \end{array} \right.$ 
for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $n - 1$ 
  do  $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{for } j \leftarrow 0 \text{ to } n - 1 \\ \text{do } E[i][j] \leftarrow \text{rem} \left( \text{quo} \left( C[i] \cdot D[j], \lambda^{n-1} \right), \lambda \right) \end{array} \right.$ 
return ( $E$ )

```

In the proposed scheme, a cellular automata based optimisation technique parallelises the three loops presented in the algorithm 2.3, causing the time complexity to be independent of the size of the input.

3 Description of the proposed algorithm

In this section, the proposed algorithm has been chalked out. First the cellular automata based modification of the matrix multiplication algorithm 2.3 is shown. Then a similar modification of the F_5 algorithm is shown which uses the CA-based matrix product to perform Gaussian elimination. Finally, the main algorithm is shown where all these presented algorithms are used in some way or the other.

3.1 Cellular automata based acceleration of the matrix multiplication algorithm

Here the main aim is to parallelise the independent loops present in algorithm 2.3 completely. There will be three first order cellular automata that can be sequentially run one after the other, each of them run for one step of temporal evolution. For the first and second loops, the grids of cells Q_{1t} and Q_{2t} are $n \times n$ arrays, meant for storing input arrays $A|_{n \times n}$ and $B|_{n \times n}$ for time instance $t = 0$. The set of states S must be a polynomial ring for this parallelised version. The neighbourhood matrix $N|_{(n-1) \times 2}$ is common to both the loops, which is

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 \\ 3 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ (n-1) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The transition function for the first loop is

$$f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \lambda^{i-1}$$

and the transition function for the second loop is

$$f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \lambda^{n-i}$$

The grid of cells for the first loop is $Q_{10}[i][j] = A[i][j]$ and that for the second loop is $Q_{20} = B[i][j]$ for time instance $t = 0$. The cellular automata (S, Q_{1t}, N, f_1) (for the first loop) and (S, Q_{2t}, N, f_2) (for the second loop) are run for only one time step simultaneously. This way all the rows of Q_{11} contain the same array $C[i]$ mentioned in algorithm 2.3 and all the rows of Q_{21} contain the same array $D[i]$.

The third cellular automaton (S, Q_{3t}, N, f_3) is meant for the third loop. Here Q_{3t} is a $n \times n$ array where $Q_{30}[i, j] = Q_{11}[n_1, i]Q_{21}[n_2, j]$ for time instance $t = 1$, n_1 and n_2 being two random numbers between 1 and n . N , the neighbourhood matrix, is a 1×2 matrix,

$$N = (0 \quad 1)$$

The transition function $f_3(x_1, x_2)$ is defined as

$$f_3(x_1, x_2) = \text{rem}\left(\text{quo}(x_1, \lambda^{n-1}), \lambda\right)$$

After running the CA for time instance $t = 2$, the array Q_{31} holds the main result, and this all happens after 2 time instances irrespective of the size of the array. So this parallelised version of the matrix multiplication algorithm takes $O(1)$ time.

3.2 Cellular automata based modification of the F_5 algorithm

A single cellular automaton CA_{F_5} will be used to accelerate the complete F_5 algorithm that calculates the Gröbner basis. The 4-tuple (S, Q_t, N, Γ) will be the CA, where S is the polynomial ring, Q_t is the array of the m polynomials (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m) in n variables and $N = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is the neighbourhood matrix. The transition function Γ will be driven by the CellularAutomataF5Algorithm presented in algorithm 3.1, as shown below.

$$\Gamma(x_1, x_2) = \text{CellularAutomataF5Algorithm}(x_1, x_2)$$

Algorithm 3.1: CELLULARAUTOMATAF5ALGORITHM(f_1, f_2)

comment: The input consists of two homogeneous polynomials (f_1, f_2)

comment: with degrees d_1 and d_2 respectively.

comment: The output is the elements of degree $\max(d_1, d_2) + 1$ of

comment: the reduced Gröbner basis of (f_1, f_2)

$D \leftarrow \max(d_1, d_2) + 1$

return ($F_5\text{Algorithm}(f_1, f_2)$)

It is known that the Gaussian elimination can be solved by an equivalent matrix multiplication [23]. And that problem can be solved using cellular automata based solution presented in section 3.1. At time instance $t = 1$, the overall results come in all the cells of the grid. This particular algorithm is much faster and reduces the overall scheme as shown in section 4.

3.3 The proposed algorithm

Now one is fully ready to understand the proposed algorithm. This procedure takes the lapse function $f(r)$ of the charged spherically symmetric black hole and the gauge potential as the input and produces an expression in first-order logic that represents the classification of geodesics of the charged particles around the black hole. Firstly, the constraints equivalent to equation 5 are obtained and equivalent polynomial constraints P_{cx} are obtained. Then the polynomials involved in P_{cx} are given to the cellular automaton CA_{F_5} to obtain the Gröbner basis. Then by means of the interval arithmetic rules explained in section 2.3, one arrives at the required result.

Algorithm 3.2: BLACKHOLEGEODESICCLASSIFIER($f(r), A_t(r)$)

comment: $f(r)$ is the lapse function of the black hole and

comment: $A_t(r)$ is the gauge potential

$$d(r) \leftarrow f'(r)$$

$$e(r) \leftarrow A_t'(r)^2$$

$$a(r) \leftarrow f(r)d(r)\epsilon^2 e(r) \left(1 + d(r)\right) + 2f(r)d(r) - 1$$

$$b(r) \leftarrow 2\epsilon f(r)d(r)$$

$$c(r) \leftarrow 4f(r)d(r) + \epsilon^2 e(r)d(r) - 2$$

$$C_{ex} \leftarrow c(r) \geq 0 \wedge \left(a(r) \geq 0 \vee a(r)^2 \leq b(r)^2 c(r) \right)$$

$P_{cx} \leftarrow$ Obtain equivalent polynomial constraints P_{cx} from C_{ex}

$(f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_m) \leftarrow$ Set of polynomials involved in P_{cx}

$CA_{F_5} \leftarrow (S, (f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_m), (0 \ 1), \Gamma)$

Run CA_{F_5} for one time instance

$B \leftarrow$ Apply interval arithmetic rules on the cells of the grid to obtain the expression

return (B)

The operations unexplained in the algorithm 3.2 are the extraction of equivalent polynomial constraints P_{cx} and the application of interval arithmetic rules. There are several hundreds of simplification rules existent [19], which can all be formulated in an appropriate S-attribute grammar G_s that enables comfortable LALR(1) parsing. Parsing the expression with the help of G_s can bring these operations into effect. In section 3.4 a working example of the algorithm has been shown and in section 4, the time complexity of this algorithm is explained in detail.

3.4 Working example

One good working example is the Reissner-Nördstrom anti de-Sitter black hole with lapse function $f(r)$ and a gauge function $A_t(r)$ (also mentioned in table 1)

$$f(r) = 1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{Q^2}{r^2} + \frac{r^2}{l^2}$$

$$A_t(r) = \frac{Q}{r}$$

where M is the mass of the black hole, Q is the charge of the black hole and $\Lambda = \frac{-3}{l^2}$, Λ being the cosmological constant. As has been described in algorithm 3.2, the corresponding functions $d(r), e(r), a(r), b(r)$ and $c(r)$ are given by,

$$d(r) = \frac{2M}{r^2} - \frac{2Q^2}{r^3} + \frac{2r}{l^2}$$

$$e(r) = \frac{Q^2}{r^4}$$

$$a(r) = \frac{4(r^4 + l^2Mr - l^2Q^2)(r^4 + l^2Q^2 + 2Ml^2r - l^2r^2)}{l^4r^5} - 1$$

$$+ 2Q^2\epsilon^2 \frac{(l^2Q^2 - l^2Mr - r^4)(l^2Q^2 - 2l^2Mr + l^2r^2 + r^4)(2l^2Q^2 - 2l^2Mr - l^2r^3 - 2r^4)}{l^6r^{12}}$$

$$b(r) = \frac{4\epsilon}{l^4r^5}(r^4 + l^2Mr - l^2Q^2)(l^2Q^2 - 2l^2Mr + l^2r^2 + r^4)$$

$$c(r) = \frac{2Q^2\epsilon^2}{r^7} \left(\frac{r^4}{l^2} + Mr - Q^2 \right) + \frac{8}{l^4r^5}(r^4 + l^2Mr - l^2Q^2)(l^2Q^2 - 2l^2Mr + l^2r^2 + r^4) - 2$$

Having all of these functions handy, the constraint C_{ex} is expressed as $c(r) \geq 0 \wedge \left(a(r) \geq 0 \vee a(r)^2 \leq b(r)^2 c(r) \right)$. The equivalent polynomial constraint P_{cx} is given as

$$f_1(r) \geq 0 \wedge \left(f_2(r) \leq 0 \vee f_3(r) \leq 0 \right)$$

where $f_1(r)$, $f_2(r)$ and $f_3(r)$ are the polynomials defined below.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(r) = & -8l^6 M^3 Q^2 r^3 \epsilon^2 + 20l^6 M^2 Q^4 r^2 \epsilon^2 - 4l^6 M^2 Q^2 r^5 \epsilon^2 \\
& + 4l^6 M^2 Q^2 r^4 \epsilon^2 - 8l^6 M^2 r^9 - 16l^6 M Q^6 r \epsilon^2 \\
& + 6l^6 M Q^4 r^4 \epsilon^2 - 8l^6 M Q^4 r^3 \epsilon^2 + 12l^6 M Q^2 r^8 + 2l^6 M Q^2 r^6 \epsilon^2 + 4l^6 M r^{10} + 4l^6 Q^8 \epsilon^2 \\
& - 2l^6 Q^6 r^3 \epsilon^2 + 4l^6 Q^6 r^2 \epsilon^2 - 4l^6 Q^4 r^7 - 2l^6 Q^4 r^5 \epsilon^2 - 4l^6 Q^2 r^9 - l^6 r^{12} - 12l^4 M^2 Q^2 r^6 \epsilon^2 \\
& + 16l^4 M Q^4 r^5 \epsilon^2 - 2l^4 M Q^2 r^8 \epsilon^2 + 8l^4 M Q^2 r^7 \epsilon^2 - 4l^4 M r^{12} - 4l^4 Q^6 r^4 \epsilon^2 - 8l^4 Q^4 r^6 \\
& \epsilon^2 + 2l^4 Q^2 r^9 \epsilon^2 + 4l^4 r^{13} - 4l^2 Q^4 r^8 \epsilon^2 + 2l^2 Q^2 r^{11} \epsilon^2 + 4l^2 Q^2 r^{10} \epsilon^2 + 4l^2 \\
& r^{15} + 4Q^2 r^{12} \epsilon^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_2(r) = & 8l^4 M^2 r^4 - 12l^4 M Q^2 r^3 - l^4 M Q^2 r \epsilon^2 \\
& - 4l^4 M r^5 + 4l^4 Q^4 r^2 + l^4 Q^4 \epsilon^2 + 4l^4 Q^2 r^4 + l^4 r^7 + 4l^2 M r^7 - l^2 Q^2 r^4 \epsilon^2 - 4l^2 r^8 - 4r^{10}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_3(r) = & 16\epsilon^2(8r^9 - Q^4 \epsilon^2)r^{24} + 16l^2 \epsilon^2(24(r - M)r^{10} \\
& + 2Q^2(\epsilon^2 - 1)r^7 - Q^4(r + 2) \\
& \epsilon^2 r^2 + 2Q^6 \epsilon^2) \\
& r^{20} + 4l^4(-4r^{14} - 4((24r^2 - 2)Q^4 \\
& + r(24r^2 + r + 4) - 2M(36r^2 + 1))Q^2 + 2r^4 \\
& (12M^2 + 12rM + (r - 12)r^2))\epsilon^2 r^7 \\
& + Q^2(8(2r - M)r^8 - Q^2(-24M^2 - 4(r - 4)rM + r^2(r(8r^2 + r + 8) + 4)) \\
& r^2 + 4Q^4(r(r + 6) - 8M)r + 4Q^6) \\
& \epsilon^4 r^{16} + 8l^6(4(M - r)r^{15} + (8Q^6 + 16r(-6r^3 + r + M(6r^2 - 2)) \\
& Q^4 - r^2(4(72r^2 - 5)M^2 \\
& - 4r(96r^2 + r - 2)M + r^2(96r^2 + 3r + 4))Q^2 + 8(M - r)r^5(22M^2 - 8r \\
& M + (r - 2)r^2))\epsilon^2 \\
& r^7 + Q^2(4(-5M^2 + 2rM + r^2)r^9 + Q^2(-(16r^2 + r + 2)r^4 + M(r(32 \\
& r^2 + r - 4) - 8)r^2 + 2M^2(5r + 4) \\
& r + 8M^3)r^3 + 4Q^6(8M + (r - 2)r)r - 8Q^8 - 8Q^4(r^7 - r^5 + (2M - 1) \\
& r^4 + 4M^2 r^2))\epsilon^4) \\
& r^{12} + 4l^8(2(4Q^4 + 4r(r - 3M)Q^2 + (r - 2)r^4 + 6M^2 r^2)r^{14} + (16(6r^2 - 1) \\
& Q^8 + 8r(24r^3 - 72Mr^2 \\
& + r^2 + 6M)Q^6 + 2r^2(12(48r^2 - 1)M^2 - 12r(24r^2 + r + 2)M \\
& + r^2(8r^3 + 3r + 12))Q^4 + r^3((r(16r - 95) \\
& - 2)r^4 + 12M^2(24r^2 + r + 4)r - 8M^3(108r^2 + 1) \\
& - 24M(2r^5 - 12r^4 + r^2))Q^2 + 8r^6(-r^5 + 3M \\
& (M + 4)r^3 - 36M^2 r^2 + 12M^3 r + 24
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& M^4))\epsilon^2 r^7 + Q^2 \\
& (4Q^{10} - 8r^2(r+2)Q^8 + 2r^2(8r^5 + r^4 + 12(M-1) \\
& r^2 + 48Mr - 24M^2)Q^6 + 2r^3((r+6)r^4 - 3M(r(8r^2 + r + 4) - 8) \\
& r^2 - 6M^2(r+12)r + 40M^3)Q^4 - r^4((24r+1)r^6 + 12 \\
& M(1-4r^2)r^4 - 3M^2(r(8r^2 + r + 8) - 8)r^2 + 4M^3(r-16)r + \\
& 36M^4)Q^2 + 8Mr^{10}(M^2 - 6rM + 3r^2)) \\
& \epsilon^4 r^8 + 4l^{10}(2(r-M)(4Q^4 + 4r \\
& (r-3M)Q^2 + r^2(r^3 - 4Mr + 8M^2))r^{15} \\
& + (-8Q^{10} - 32r(-3r^3 + r + M(3r^2 - 2))Q^8 + 2r^2(12 \\
& (24r^2 - 7)M^2 - 4r(96r^2 + r - 18)M + 3r^2(32r^2 + r - 4)) \\
& Q^6 + 4r^3((4r(r+6) + 1)r^4 - 2M \\
& (r(2r(r+54) + 3) - 6)r^2 + 6M^2(84r^2 + r - 8)r + M^3 \\
& (44 - 312r^2))Q^4 + r^4((16r+1)r^6 - M(r(64r+193) + 4)r^4 + 6M^2 \\
& (r(8r(r+24) + 3) - 4)r^2 - 16M^3(132r^2 + r - 5) \\
& r + 64M^4(18r^2 - 1))Q^2 - 16M(M-r)(2M-r)r^7(r^3 - 6Mr + 12M^2)) \\
& \epsilon^2 r^7 + 2Q^2(Q^2 - Mr)(Q^2 + r(r-2M)) \\
& (4M(4M-3r)r^9 + Q^2((12r+1)r^5 - M(20r^2 + r - 6) \\
& r^3 - 8M^2(r-1)r - 12M^3)r^3 + 2Q^4((2r^2 - 3)r^3 \\
& + M(5r-8)r + 14M^2)r^2 - 2Q^6(10M + (r-4)r)r + 4 \\
& Q^8)\epsilon^4)r^4 - l^{12}((4Q^4 + 4r(r-3M)Q^2 \\
& + r^2(r^3 - 4Mr + 8M^2))^2r^{14} + 4(Mr - Q^2)(Q^2 + r(r-2M)) \\
& (4Q^4 + 4r(r-3M)Q^2 + r^2(r^3 - 4Mr + 8M^2)) \\
& ((2-8r^2)Q^4 - r(8r^3 - 24M \\
& r^2 + r^2 + 2M)Q^2 + 8Mr^4(r-2M))\epsilon^2 r^7 + 4Q^2 \\
& (Q^2 - Mr)^2(Q^2 + r(r-2M))^2(-8Mr^8 + 4Q^6 - 4Q^4 \\
& (r^3 + 2Mr) + Q^2(8r^7 + r^6 + 4Mr^4 + 4M^2r^2))\epsilon^4)
\end{aligned}$$

The reduced Gröbner basis of the polynomial ideal (f_1, f_2, f_3) resulting from the grid of CA_{F_3} is the set $G = \{l - 6Q, l - 2Q, r - \sqrt{2}Q, r^2 - 3Mr + 2Q^2, r^2 - 3Mr + 2Q^2 + 2q^2, 9M^2 - 8Q^2 - q^2, f_4(l, M, Q), f_5(l, M, Q, q)\}$ where

$$f_4(r) = 27l^2M^4 + l^4M^2 - 36l^2M^2Q^2 + 8l^2Q^4 - l^4Q^2 - 16Q^6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_5(r) = & q^8 Q^6 + q^6(32Q^6 - 8l^2 Q^4) + q^4(16l^4 Q^2 + 432l^2 M^2 Q^2 - 160l^2 Q^4 + 384Q^6) \\
& + q^2(2048Q^6 - 1024l^2 Q^4 + 4608l^2 M^2 Q^2 - 3456l^2 M^2 Q^2 + 128l^4 Q^2 - 128M^2 l^4) \\
& + 4096Q^6 - 2048l^2 Q^4 + 9216l^2 M^2 Q^2 - 6912M^4 l^2 + 256l^4 Q^2 - 256M^2 l^4
\end{aligned}$$

Now using interval arithmetic, one can verify that the resulting Boolean expression is equivalent to the table of classification of geodesics of the RNAdS black hole known in literature [18].

4 Analysis of the asymptotic complexity

One of the lowest possible bounds achieved on the complexity of symbolic differentiation is $O(n\nu^3)$ for an algebraic expression with n variables and ν nodes in its expression graph [38]. With this in mind, let us assume that there are n variables in the lapse function with ν_1 nodes. Let there be ν_2 nodes in the expression graph of the gauge function as well. So the time taken to obtain the functions $d(r)$ and $e(r)$ would be $O\left(n(\nu_1^3 + \nu_2^3)\right)$. An empirical estimate on the number of nodes in $d(r)$ in the algorithm 3.2 would be $O(\nu_1)$. Assuming complete expansion without the simplification of a polynomial product, the number of nodes $e(r)$ would be $O(\nu_2^2)$. So the expressions $a(r)$, $b(r)$ and $c(r)$ would contain $O(\nu_1^3 \nu_2^2)$, $O(\nu_1^3)$ and $O(\nu_1^2 + \nu_1 \nu_2^2)$ nodes respectively. So the constraint C_{ex} would asymptotically contain $O(\nu_1^3 \nu_2^2)$ nodes, and so would the equivalent polynomial constraint P_{ex} . So obtaining the polynomial constraints and the set of polynomials using the appropriate S-attribute grammar would consume $O(\nu_1^3 \nu_2^2)$ time. As already seen in section 2.3, for an ideal with m polynomials in n variables with a maximum degree D , the asymptotic time complexity of the F_5 algorithm is $O\left(mD^{(n+D-1)\omega}\right)$, being the ω is the matrix multiplication exponent. In the proposed cellular automata based modification of the F_5 algorithm 3.1, the Gaussian elimination can be reduced to an instance of the matrix multiplication problem, which can be solved efficiently using the cellular automata explained in section 3.1 in constant time. If that is the case, then for the proposed procedure, $\omega = 0$. Also, in each cell of the grid of the cellular automaton CA_{F_5} , there are exactly 2 polynomials each on which the F_5 algorithm is being used. Thus, the time complexity of the cellular automaton CA_{F_5} is $O(D)$, D being the maximum degree of the polynomials involved. Since there are $O(m)$ polynomials in the reduced Gröbner basis of the grid, the time taken by an S-attribute grammar emulating the interval arithmetic rules is $O(m)$. So the overall time complexity of the black hole geodesic classifier is $O\left(n(\nu_1^3 + \nu_2^3) + \nu_1^3 \nu_2^2 + D + m\right)$.

5 Conclusion

In this article, the problem of automatically finding all possible circular geodesics around a given black hole by means of symbolic computation has been stated. Earlier approaches to solving the Gröbner basis problems have been discussed, and their time complexities discussed. Also, a novel algorithm for matrix multiplication in polynomial rings has also been presented and explained in terms of efficacy in the additive complexity measure. A cellular automata based solution to the stated problem has also been suggested, along with a brief discussion on its time complexity and a working example. In future, the application of this algorithm is expected in finding correlations between geometry, thermodynamics and other such features of the black holes. Also, further improvements can be made on the symbolic differentiation complexity by means of an appropriate cellular automata based model.

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